

**Circular
Cities & Regions
Initiative**

Knowledge Hub

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Ethics and Data Management Plan-1 /D1.3

WP 1, T 1.5

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Technical references

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- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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Table of contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. Introduction.....	8
1.1. Project overview	8
1.2. Deliverable Purpose & Scope.....	9
1.3. Target audience	9
1.4. Applicable documents	9
1.5. Acronyms	10
1.6. Definitions.....	10
2. Data summary	2
2.1. Data Collection and Anonymisation.....	2
2.2. Collaboration and Data Usage	2
2.3. Handling of Data from Professionals and Collaborating Entities.....	2
2.4. Security and Confidentiality of Data.....	3
2.5. Data Retention and Access.....	3
2.6. Risk Management and Regulatory Compliance	3
2.7. Review and Update of the Data Management Plan	3
3. Data generation and collection.....	3
4. Fair Data	11
4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	11
4.2. Metadata	11
4.3. Making data accessible	15
4.4. Making data interoperable	16
4.5. Increase data re-use	17
5. Allocation of resources.....	17
5.1. Costs.....	17
5.1. Responsibilities.....	18

6. Data security	18
6.1. Compliance with GDPR	19
6.1.1. Purpose	19
6.1.2. Accuracy	19
6.1.3. Integrity and Confidentiality	20
6.1.4. Accountability	20
6.1.5. Personal Information	20
6.1.6. Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation	20
6.1.7. Informed consent	20
7. Ethics	21
7.1. Data protection	21
7.1.1. Informed consent	23
7.1.2. Confidentiality and Anonymisation	23
7.1.3. Data security	24
7.1.4. Regulatory Compliance	24
7.1.5. Data integrity	25
7.1.6. Participant Rights	25
7.1.7. Disclosure and Transparency	25
7.1.8. Ethical Review	26
7.2. CCRI Knowledge Hub Ethics Self-assessment	26
7.2.1. Objectives	26
7.2.2. Methodology	26
7.2.3. Potential impact	26
7.2.4. Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislation	27
7.3. Ethical Management Plan: definition and main aspects	28
7.3.1. Connexion to CCRI Knowledge Hub WPs	29
7.4. CCRI Knowledge Hub ethical monitoring plan	30
7.4.1. Ethical requirements prior to activities with participants involvement	30
7.4.2. Ethics monitoring tools	31
8. Conclusions	32

9. Annexes	33
9.1. Annex 1: Questionnaire regarding ethical aspects and data protection	33
9.2. Annex 2: Questionnaire to monitor compliance with CCRI Knowledge Hub ethical standards	34

List of Tables

Table 1 Descriptive Metadata	12
Table 2 Structural Metadata Template	13
Table 3 Administrative metadata	14
Table 4 Ethics monitoring tools – actions & responsibilities	31

List of Figures

Figure 1 CCRI Knowledge Hub's formula	8
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Data Management Plan (DMP) establishes a comprehensive framework for data governance throughout the CCRI Knowledge Hub project lifecycle (Task 1.5). The document outlines systematic protocols for data collection, processing, sharing, storage, access, and protection whilst ensuring strict adherence to GDPR compliance and ethical standards. Additionally, it addresses ethics management, covering legal and normative ethical challenges encountered during project implementation. Our systematic approach has demonstrated data integrity through centralised management via SharePoint (Office 365) and standardised data collection protocols across all project deliverables. The implementation of our four-category data classification system has streamlined data processing whilst maintaining regulatory compliance. Lessons learnt include the importance of early stakeholder engagement in data governance decisions and the value of consistent anonymisation procedures across all project activities. Technical challenges in data integration across multiple project partners were addressed by implementing unified storage solutions and access protocols. Moreover, we have established robust data security measures including restricted access controls and comprehensive anonymisation procedures. Standardised templates for data collection have been deployed across all project tasks, ensuring consistency and quality. Ethics management protocols have been integrated into all data processing activities, with particular attention to informed consent procedures and data minimisation principles. Regular updates to this DMP will reflect evolving project needs and regulatory requirements throughout the remaining project phases.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Project overview

CCRI Knowledge Hub aims at increasing the impact of the existing Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) by enlarging the network of involved stakeholders, bringing together the knowledge and critical mass already developed around Circular Economy (CE) implementation and building upon the CE stakeholder platform. The goal is to promote and make the CE concept a reality in EU cities and regions, in particular in those in the early stage of CE transition.

To reach its objective, CCRI Knowledge Hub will act as a “Knowledge Hub”, leveraging existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of CE in EU cities and regions. CCRI Knowledge Hub’s formula is based on three principles: (a) easy access to systematised workable knowledge; (b) tailored mentoring according to users’ needs and (c) effective awareness-raising to make the CE more desirable, that build upon four main dimensions: (i) Public engagement; (ii) Innovation and technology; (iii) Business models and financial support; and (iv) Impact evaluation.

Figure 1 CCRI Knowledge Hub's formula

CCRI Knowledge Hub gathers a multidisciplinary expert consortium of 11 partners from 6 EU countries (research and technological centres, universities, research organizations, international networks and associations, regional authorities as well as specialized companies and SMEs) that bring in complementary skills and competences to achieve the project’s objectives.

Project basic data:

- Starting date: 1st of January 2024
- Closing date: 31st of December 2026
- Duration: 36 months.
- Maximum grant amount (as stated in the annex 2 of the Grant Agreement, GA): 2.612.932,04€.
- Project number: 101135174

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- Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-CircBio-01-1
- Type of action: Coordination and Support Action (CSA)

1.2. Deliverable Purpose & Scope

An Ethics and Data Management Plan – DMP (D1.3) has been developed by project partners at the beginning of the project (internal version delivered in month 6, final version delivered and submitted to the Funding & Tenders' by month 18) outlining the data to be collected and how they will be collected, processed, shared, storage, accessed and protected. The plan includes information about data management during and after the project, methodology and standards to be used, access requirements, etc. and process and requirements to ensure ethical standards in all the activities implemented. The DMP will be updated along the project implementation (these updates will be reflected in D5.3 – Ethics and Data Management Plan-2 to be delivered in month 36, that is, at the end of the project). Ethics management will cover both the legal and the normative ethical challenges through an internal participatory reflection process. Among others, the privacy of personal data collected during all the participatory activities conducted, its legal approach, the security in saving and sharing the information, the role of CE in societal transformation and its ethical implication, the appropriateness of CCRI Knowledge Hub concerning the RRI framework, or social responsibility behind Open Data and public disclosure of (anonymised) results. The results of this task are reported in this D1.3 in month 18 (June 2025).

1.3. Target audience

- Project team members involved in collecting, processing, analysing, or storing data
- Research partners collaborating on the CCRI Knowledge Hub project
- Administrative staff handling participant information and communications
- Project managers overseeing compliance with data protection regulations
- IT personnel responsible for implementing technical security measures
- External evaluators assessing the project's data governance practices
- Project stakeholders with interest in how data is managed and protected

1.4. Applicable documents

- GDPR (Regulation EU 2016/679) - The primary regulation governing data protection
- CCRI Knowledge Hub Grant Agreement - Outlining project commitments related to data
- Institutional Data Protection Policies of participating organizations
- European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA, 2017)
- Deliverable D.1.1. Project Management Handbook-1- For alignment with overall project objectives

- Consortium Agreement - Defining data-sharing arrangements between partners
- National data protection laws relevant to participating countries

1.5. Acronyms

CE	Circular Economy	FAIR	Findable, Accessible, interoperable, and Re-usable
D	Deliverable	GA	General Assembly
DPA	Data Processing Agreement	GDPR	General Data Protection
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment	JCA	Joint Controllership Agreement
DIS	Data Integration System	M	Month
DAC	Data Access Committee	ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
DMP	Data Management Plan	PC	Project Coordinator
DPO	Data Protection Officer	WP	Work Package
EC	European Commission		

1.6. Definitions

- **Identification and Contact Information:** Names, surnames, email addresses, phone numbers, postal addresses, and fiscal identification numbers where required for employment purposes.
- **Demographic and Professional Background:** Gender, educational qualifications, English language proficiency, curriculum vitae details, professional experience, and geographic location data
- **Social Media Data:** Information from social media platforms, including profile details, posts, connections, and interactions.
- **Participation and Contribution Data:** Reports, analyses, feedback, opinions about the project processes and outcomes, digital interactions with project systems and platforms, and other contributions made by participants.

2. Data summary

2.1. Data Collection and Anonymisation

The project is primarily working with information obtained from databases. Within these databases, the data is anonymised, preventing partners from accessing personal information about the subjects. Before using the data for any analysis or research, it is ensured that they have been adequately anonymised to protect individuals' privacy, in compliance with Article 25 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union (EU) (Regulation 679/2016).

Personal data will be subject to de-identification and site control, unless written informed consent for very clearly defined research activities is specifically obtained.

Data formats and data types produced under the project depend on how data will be gathered, and the software used for their analysis. Clearly, several data types require different file types. As general guidelines, CCRI Knowledge Hub recommends:

- avoiding the use of property software format when possible;
- in case of data files in different formats, converting the data to the most common data format.

2.2. Collaboration and Data Usage

During the development of the project, collaboration is anticipated with professionals, companies, and also private individuals. Given the nature of the project, there is no requirement for data of special or sensitive categories, but rather basic data for identification purposes and regarding the role in the CE.

2.3. Handling of Data from Professionals and Collaborating Entities

From professionals and collaborating entities, only the necessary data required for the fulfilment of professional relationships with the project is being obtained. This includes basic information such as names, professional affiliations, and relevant contact details. It is ensured that this data is used exclusively for the purposes intended in the project and handled in accordance with the relevant data protection laws and regulations, particularly the GDPR of the EU.

2.4. Security and Confidentiality of Data

Appropriate security measures are implemented to protect the confidentiality and integrity of the data collected and processed during the project. This includes restricted access to the data only to authorised personnel and the adoption of robust information security practices to prevent unauthorised access, disclosure, or loss of data, in accordance with Article 32 of the GDPR of the EU.

2.5. Data Retention and Access

Procedures are established for the secure retention of data during the project and after its completion. Additionally, methods for accessing the data and the conditions under which they can be shared with other researchers or stakeholders will be clearly documented, in compliance with the principles of accountability and transparency of the GDPR of the EU.

2.6. Risk Management and Regulatory Compliance

A risk assessment is being conducted to identify potential threats to the security and confidentiality of the data, as well as to ensure compliance with relevant data protection regulations, including the GDPR of the EU. Mitigation measures will be implemented as necessary to address any identified risks and comply with the requirements of the GDPR of the EU.

2.7. Review and Update of the Data Management Plan

This Ethics and Data Management Plan will be reviewed and updated as necessary throughout the project to ensure its continued relevance and effectiveness in protecting and managing data ethically and in accordance with applicable regulations, including the GDPR of the EU.

The official dates to deliver an updated version of this document is: D5.3 month 36

3. Data generation and collection

In this section project deliverables and their relationship with data generation, collection and treatment are outlined. The information is shown in tables for the sake of simplicity and to present the information in a straightforward way.

NAME: D1.4 – Clustering activities-1 & D5.4 – Clustering activities-2 (related to task 1.6 and 5.6)				
Type	Dissemination Level	Lead Beneficiary	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2

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R — report	PU	KVC	EBN	EURADA
Does this output involve personal data?		YES		
For deliverable D1.4, consists of a description of the clustering activities with other EU projects selected under CircBio 01-1 during the first 18 months of the project. Same applies for D.5.4. which will consist of a description of the clustering activities during the last 18 months of the project.				
What types of data are generated/processed ?		Identification and Contact Information	X	
		Demographic and Professional Background		
		Social Media Data		
		Participation and Contribution Data	X	
What types of data are required ?		Identification and Contact Information	X	
		Demographic and Professional Background	X	
		Social Media Data		
		Participation and Contribution Data	X	
Are there measures in place to ensure compliance with data protection regulations during the generation and collection of personal data?		Data Minimisation	X	
		Informed Consent	*1	
		Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation		
		Data Security Measures	X	
		Regular Audits and Compliance Checks	X	
Data Management				
Data Generation Method		Meetings, interviews, collaboration activities with EU project representatives		
Responsible Parties		All CCRI Knowledge Hub partners		
Anonymisation Applied?		When necessary		
Storage Location		SharePoint (Office 365)		
Access Rights		CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium		

NAME: Activity: Task 2.1. Identification and compilation of CE projects/initiatives Output related: D.2.1. CE projects/initiatives, GPs & less successful cases				
Type	Dissemination Level	Lead Beneficiary	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
R — report	PU	CETEC	FILSE	KVC
Does this output involve personal data?		YES		

¹ Informed consent will be required if mandatory, information based on contract of legitimate interest.

Data from 150 projects was collected through a dedicated template for identification and compilation of CE projects/initiatives.		
What types of data are generated/processed ?	Identification and Contact Information	X
	Demographic and Professional Background	X
	Social Media Data	
	Participation and Contribution Data	
What types of data are required ?	Identification and Contact Information	X
	Demographic and Professional Background	
	Social Media Data	X
	Participation and Contribution Data	
Are there measures in place to ensure compliance with data protection regulations during the generation and collection of personal data?	Data Minimisation	
	Informed Consent	X
	Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation	
	Data Security Measures	X
	Regular Audits and Compliance Checks	
Data Management		
Data Generation Method	User input through dedicated template	
Responsible Parties	All CCRI Knowledge Hub partners	
Anonymisation Applied?	YES	
Storage Location	SharePoint (Office 365) & CCRI website	
Access Rights	CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium	

NAME: Task 2.2. Identification of further user-friendly CE resources. Output related: D.2.2. Resources compilation to support a successful transition to a circular economy in cities/regions (Folder with materials, tools and resources)

Type	Dissemination Level	Lead Beneficiary	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
OTHER	PU	CETEC	UVEG	KVC
Does this output involve personal data?		NO		
Research and evaluation of user-friendly publicly available resources (tools and materials, including synergetic local policy plans) related to circular economy at EU level. Resources classified according to 4 key dimensions: (i) Public engagement; (ii) Innovation and technologies; (iii) Business models and market assessments; (iv) Impact evaluation.				
What types of data are generated/processed ?	Identification and Contact Information			
	Demographic and Professional Background			
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
	Identification and Contact Information			

What types of data are required?	Demographic and Professional Background	
	Social Media Data	
	Participation and Contribution Data	
Are there measures in place to ensure compliance with data protection regulations during the generation and collection of personal data?	Data Minimisation	X
	Informed Consent	
	Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation	
	Data Security Measures	X
	Regular Audits and Compliance Checks	X
Data Management		
Data Generation Method	Research and evaluation of public resources	
Responsible Parties	CETEC (lead), All CCRI Knowledge Hub partners	
Anonymisation Applied?	N/A (public data only)	
Storage Location	SharePoint (Office 365)	
Access Rights	CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium	

NAME: D.3.1. CCRI Knowledge Hub Support Pathways (related to task 3.1)				
Type	Dissemination Level	Lead Beneficiary	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
R — report	PU	UVEG	ALDA	KVC
Does this output involve personal data?	YES			
This deliverable reflects the support pathways of the selected cities and regions to be part of the CCRI network during the first round. To deliver the support pathways input from civil servants, public decision-makers etc have been collected. Their data was collected but not included in the deliverable.				
What types of data are generated/processed?	Identification and Contact Information			X
	Demographic and Professional Background			X
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
What types of data are required?	Identification and Contact Information			X
	Demographic and Professional Background			X
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
Are there measures in place to ensure compliance with data protection regulations during the generation and collection of personal data?	Data Minimisation			X
	Informed Consent			X
	Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation			X
	Data Security Measures			X
	Regular Audits and Compliance Checks			X

Data Management	
Data Generation Method	Mentors selection process, interviews with cities and regions responsible
Responsible Parties	CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium
Anonymisation Applied?	YES
Storage Location	SharePoint (Office 365)
Access Rights	CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium

NAME: D3.3 Delivery of first services (1st 18 months of the project) & D.6.1 Delivery of services (2nd 18 months of the project) (related to tasks 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6)

Type	Dissemination Level	Lead Beneficiary	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
R — report	PU	UVEG	ALDA	KVC
Does this output involve personal data?	YES			
Information on the implementation of the workshop/seminars and the provision of the first mentoring services was reported in this deliverable. All information has been anonymised as no personal data appears in the deliverable, but the activities themselves will require and generate personal data. Satisfaction surveys to mentees are being conducted, collecting their views and opinions on the CCRI Knowledge Hub services.				
What types of data are generated/processed ?	Identification and Contact Information			X
	Demographic and Professional Background			X
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
What types of data are required ?	Identification and Contact Information			X
	Demographic and Professional Background			X
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
Are there measures in place to ensure compliance with data protection regulations during the generation and collection of personal data?	Data Minimisation			X
	Informed Consent			X
	Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation			X
	Data Security Measures			X
	Regular Audits and Compliance Checks			X
Data Management				
Data Generation Method	Workshop/seminar activities, mentoring sessions, participant interactions			
Responsible Parties	CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium			
Anonymisation Applied?	YES			
Storage Location	SharePoint (Office 365)			

Access Rights	CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium
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NAME: D.3.4. Mentoring Guide and task 3.3				
Type	Dissemination Level	Lead Beneficiary	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
R — report	PU	KVC	CETEC	INV
Does this output involve personal data?	YES (during programme management activities, but not included in the deliverable itself)			
<p>For D3.4, which is a user-friendly, operational, practical ad hoc guide developed for experts who will be mentors in charge of providing mentoring services and for mentees who will receive the mentoring, both generated data and required data can be identified according to the provided definitions. The deliverable itself doesn't include data from mentors, but the templates for their contracts and guidelines to support the mentees. The related task collects data from candidates for the mentoring programme, their CVs, and monitor the contracts signature. All this information do not appear in the D3.4. A common call has been launched together with the CCRI, with its correspondent privacy statement. In relation to the mentees, no personal data is collected nor generated.</p>				
What types of data are generated/processed?	Identification and Contact Information			X
	Demographic and Professional Background			X
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
What types of data are required?	Identification and Contact Information			X
	Demographic and Professional Background			X
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			
Are there measures in place to ensure compliance with data protection regulations during the generation and collection of personal data?	Data Minimisation			X
	Informed Consent			X
	Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation			X
	Data Security Measures			X
	Regular Audits and Compliance Checks			X
Data Management				
Data Generation Method	Expression of Interest applications, CV collection, contract monitoring			
Responsible Parties	UVEG, KVC, CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium			
Anonymisation Applied?	YES			
Storage Location	SharePoint (Office 365)			
Access Rights	CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium			

NAME: D4.2 – D&C activities and impact analysis-1 & D.7.2 D&C activities and impact analysis-2				
Type	Dissemination Level	Lead Beneficiary	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
R — report	PU	ICONS	INV	KVC
Does this output involve personal data?	NO			
<p>For the deliverables consisting of a report describing and evaluating the D&C activities carried out during the implementation of the project in accordance with the D&C strategy, both generated and required data can be identified. As outlined in D4.1, the channels used to spread and distribute CCRI Knowledge Hub content will not be under the control and management of CCRI Knowledge Hub's consortium, the CCRI-CSO provides to CCRI Knowledge Hub the requested impact data monitored through their channels. More specifically, ICONS is periodically requiring to the CCRI-CSO updates on the contents' results in terms of views, interactions, downloads and further KPIs. Only non-sensitive and non-personal data is being collected. The type of data collected depend on the tools available to the CCRI-CSO.</p>				
What types of data are generated/processed?	Identification and Contact Information			
	Demographic and Professional Background			
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
What types of data are required?	Identification and Contact Information			
	Demographic and Professional Background			
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
Are there measures in place to ensure compliance with data protection regulations during the generation and collection of personal data?	Data Minimisation			X
	Informed Consent			NA
	Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation			NA
	Data Security Measures			X
	Regular Audits and Compliance Checks			X
Data Management				
Data Generation Method	Impact data monitoring through CCRI-CSO channels (views, interactions, downloads, KPIs)			
Responsible Parties	ICONS (data collection), CCRI-CSO (channel management)			
Anonymisation Applied?	N/A (non-personal data only)			
Storage Location	SharePoint (Office 365)			
Access Rights	CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium			

NAME: D8.2 – Policy recommendations and lessons learn

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Type	Dissemination Level	Lead Beneficiary	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
R — Document, report	PU	ALDA	UVEG	KVC
Does this output involve personal data?	YES			
For D8.2, which will consist of a report containing the project's policy recommendations and lessons learnt to be disseminated to policymakers at the EU level, local and regional authorities, CE experts and practitioners, citizens, etc., both generated data and required data can be identified. Additionally, focus groups and open consultations with relevant stakeholders will be organised to share, validate, and enrich the recommendations.				
What types of data are generated/processed ?	Identification and Contact Information			X
	Demographic and Professional Background			X
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
What types of data are required ?	Identification and Contact Information			X
	Demographic and Professional Background			X
	Social Media Data			
	Participation and Contribution Data			X
Are there measures in place to ensure compliance with data protection regulations during the generation and collection of personal data?	Data Minimisation			X
	Informed Consent			X
	Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation			X
	Data Security Measures			X
	Regular Audits and Compliance Checks			X
Data Management				
Data Generation Method	Focus groups ²			
Responsible Parties	ALDA (lead), VTT (support), All CCRI Knowledge Hub partners			
Anonymisation Applied?	YES			
Storage Location	SharePoint (Office 365)			
Access Rights	CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium			

² Focus groups involve stakeholders from industry, business, government, civil society

4. Fair Data

To ensure that research data can be used, shared, and re-used it is crucial to take care that those data are accessible, understandable, and usable. This requires clear data description, annotation, contextual information, and documentation explaining how data were created or digitised, what data mean or what their content and structure are.

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In order to make data findable, the Consortium had adopted the following naming conventions that provides a clear version number by following time sequence (the most recent the most updated version) to make data accessible, understandable, and usable:

- DATA_DELIVERABLE NUMER_FILE NAME_PROJECT NAME.FORMAT

Both the draft and final versions are numbered according to the Deliverable number shown into the List of Deliverables exposed in Annex I Part A of the Grant Agreement (Pages 16-17), adding the version code V0.x for consecutive draft versions and V1.x for consecutive versions of the final edition:

- Code for draft versions Dx.y_V0.z
- Code for final edition versions Dx.y_V1.z5

The Consortium also encourage establishing links between data collected and stored and the associated documentation, following recommendations such as the following:

- Including information within the data or document itself, e.g. in the document properties function of a file or the file header.
- Keeping a database of metadata with links to files.
- Storing a readme.txt file alongside the data which provides basic explanatory details. Txt. Files will be acceptable to explain very simple stuff like how to connect to a database, not the database explanation itself.
- Recording relevant context in lab notebooks or associated papers and reports.
- Including link to websites or web pages which explain the context of the research.

4.2. Metadata

The use of common data and metadata standards are a key aspect for semantic and technological data operability. Metadata can describe the content, context, and provenance of datasets in a standardised and structured manner, typically describing the purpose, origin, temporal characteristics, geographic location, authorship, access conditions and terms of use of a dataset. This provides structured searchable information that helps users to find existing data resources, judge whether a particular dataset is suitable for their research purpose and

provides a bibliographic record for citing data. Standard dictionaries of metadata are used for all data types produced by the data creators.

Metadata includes different types of metadata:

- Descriptive metadata (Table 1): describe a resource for the purpose of retrieval and identification. They may contain elements such as title, abstract, author or keywords, etc.
- Structural metadata (Table 2): relationships between different sets of associated data in the context of databases, such as schema describing associations between tables.
- Administrative metadata (Table 3): provides the information necessary to help process a resource. An example might be the date of creation or how a resource was created. It may contain several subgroups of administrative information. Among the most common are metadata on rights and metadata for long-term preservation. The latter is one of the primary purposes of repositories.

Table 1 Descriptive Metadata

Title	[Title of the resource]
Creator(s)	[Name(s) of the creator(s) or author(s)]
Date Created/Published	[Date when the resource was created or published]
Description	[Brief description of the resource, including its content, purpose, or significance]
Subject(s)	[Keywords or phrases that describe the topic(s) or subject(s) of the resource]
Language	[Language(s) of the resource]
Format	[Format of the resource, such as text, image, audio, video, etc.]
Extent	[Physical or digital size of the resource, duration for audio/video, number of pages for text, etc.]
Publisher	[Entity or individual responsible for making the resource available]
Rights	[Information about the copyright status or usage rights of the resource]

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Identifier	[Unique identifier or URL assigned to the resource]
Source	[Information about the origin or source of the resource]
Relation	[Relationship of the resource to other resources, if applicable]
Coverage	[Geographical, temporal, or thematic coverage of the resource]
Audience	[Intended audience or target demographic for the resource]
Contributor(s)	[Names of individuals or organizations that contributed to the creation or development of the resource]
Version	[Version number or information about any revisions or updates]
Keywords	[Additional keywords or phrases relevant to the resource]

Table 2 Structural Metadata Template

Resource Identifier	[Unique identifier for the resource]
Hierarchy	[Description of the hierarchical structure of the resource, such as chapters, sections, pages, etc.]
Sequence	[Order or sequence of the components within the resource]
Navigation	[Information about how to navigate or access different parts of the resource]
Relationships	[Information about the relationships between different components or parts of the resource]
File Format	[Format of the resource, including file extensions and MIME types]
Duration	[For multimedia resources, the duration or length of the resource]

Resolution	[For images or videos, the resolution or dimensions]
Bit Rate	[For audio or video files, the bit rate or quality]
Compression	[If applicable, information about compression methods used]
Checksums	[Checksum values to verify data integrity]
Annotations	[Information about any annotations, bookmarks, or metadata embedded within the resource]
Access Restrictions	[Any access restrictions or permissions associated with specific components or parts of the resource]
Version	[Version number or information about any revisions or updates]
Keywords	[Additional keywords or phrases relevant to the resource]

Table 3 Administrative metadata

Resource Identifier	[Unique identifier for the resource]
Creator(s)	[Name(s) of the creator(s) or author(s)]
Contributor(s)	[Names of individuals or organizations that contributed to the creation or development of the resource]
Creation Date	[Date when the resource was created]
Publisher	[Entity or individual responsible for making the resource available]
Publication Date	[Date when the resource was published or made available]
Modification Date	[Date when the resource was last modified or updated]
Version	[Version number or information about any revisions or updates]

Publisher	[Entity or individual responsible for making the resource available]
File Format	[Format of the resource, including file extensions and MIME types]
Size	[Size of the resource in bytes or other appropriate units]
Storage Location	[Location where the resource is stored or archived]
Access Rights	[Information about access rights or permissions associated with the resource]
Preservation Metadata	[Information about preservation strategies or metadata necessary for long-term preservation]
Rights Management	[Information about rights management or access control mechanisms]
Metadata Creation	[Details about the process of creating or capturing metadata for the resource]
Metadata Standards	[Information about the metadata standards or schemas used to describe the resource]
Checksums	[Checksum values to verify data integrity]

4.3. Making data accessible

Accessibility means that metadata and data are understandable to humans and machines and may be retrievable by their identifier via a standardised communication protocol.

As foreseen in Article 16 of the Grand Agreement, the partners must grant access to each other's information, subject to the restrictions on intellectual property and any special procedures set out in Annex 5 of the GA.

Data accessibility will be further defined in the final version of this deliverable in terms of:

- Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited taking into consideration that where possible preference should be given to certified repositories supporting open access, likely the CCRI website.

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- How will access be provided and if there would be restrictions on use.
- The authentication procedure to authorise data access.

Dissemination of results:

The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Open science: open access to scientific publications:

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- At the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- Immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND), and
- Information is given via the repository about any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.
- Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

4.4. Making data interoperable

Interoperability is the ability to access and process machine-readable data from multiple sources, sometimes automatically, without that data losing meaning or integrity". To achieve this goal, data requires:

- Syntactic interoperability: widespread adoption of standard data formats, and the implementation of application programming interfaces and connectors that allow data from multiple sources to be accessed and integrated.
- Semantic interoperability: data and information must be exchanged across systems without its context and meaning being lost; and

- Search interoperability: it enables a user to conduct queries across two or more collections of data.

Thus, interoperability enables improved data usability and use. For this reason, putting in practice interoperability will be a priority for the Consortium in order to have the following benefits (among others):

- Reducing time, effort and expense spent on data collection.
- Eliminating frustration and risks associated with finding inconsistent and incomplete data.
- Making available sustainable, disaggregated data for effective decision-making.

4.5. Increase data re-use

The obtained data by developing the project could be made openly accessible if the General Assembly (GA) agrees to. The main aim is to make the data openly accessible for as long as possible. The decision on the long-term availability of the data collected and processed in the framework of the CCRI Knowledge Hub project will be taken as the data are stored.

After the completion of each task involving data collection, the data will be made openly accessible when the following requirements are met:

- Data collection and processing are completed.
- Data checking - in terms of quality control - is performed.
- The exploitation plan of the consortium partners, both in terms of scientific publications and commercial purposes, is finalised.

Discussions on licensing and re-use conditions will also be conducted by the project's GA, with the support and/or supervision of the DPO or designated data controller, if necessary.

Finally, data produced during the project will be re-usable for as long as the information they contain are relevant for further research purposes.

5. Allocation of resources

5.1. Costs

Costs related to open access to research data in the Horizon Europe programme are eligible costs.

5.1. Responsibilities

Data management responsibilities under the project are based on the following figures:

- Joint controllers. In the project there are joint controllers as there are several partners that jointly determine the purposes and means of data processing (art. 26 of the GDPR). Controllers shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is performed in accordance with the European GDPR.
- Data processors process personal data only on behalf of the controller.
- DPO provides expert professional knowledge in data protection law and IT security. The duties of the DPO includes: to inform and advise the controller or the processor and the employees who carry out processing of their obligations pursuant to the GDPR; to monitor compliance with personal data protection regulation; to provide advice where requested as regards the data protection impact assessment and monitor its performance; to cooperate with the supervisory authority; to act as the contact point for the supervisory authority on issues relating to processing, and to consult with regard to any other matter (art. 39.1 GDPR).

6. Data security

In the context of the project, robust data security measures are paramount to safeguard the integrity and confidentiality of our research results. We have implemented a comprehensive set of security mechanisms to ensure the protection of the data processed. This includes secure storage protocols, which employ encryption techniques to prevent unauthorised access. Access controls will be strictly enforced, limiting access to data to authorised personnel with specific roles and responsibilities. Regular audits and checks will be carried out to detect and promptly address any potential security vulnerabilities. In addition, a contingency plan for data backup and recovery will be put in place to mitigate the risk of data loss. These security measures collectively contribute to the overall resilience of our data management system, ensuring the protection of research results without compromising the privacy or confidentiality of individual data subjects.

Physical security, network security and security of computer systems and files will be considered and encouraged among the consortium to guarantee security of data as well as to prevent unauthorised access, changes to data, disclosure, or destruction of data.

Physical data security:

- Controlling access to buildings, rooms, cabinets where data, computers, media, or hardcopy materials are held.
- Logging the removal of, and access to, media or hardcopy material in storerooms.

- Transporting sensitive data only under exceptional circumstances, even for repair purposes; for example, giving a failed hard drive containing sensitive data to a computer manufacturer may cause a breach of security.

Network security:

- Not storing sensitive data such as those containing personal information on servers or computers connected to an external network, particularly servers that host internet services.
- Firewall protection and security-related upgrades and patches to operating systems to avoid viruses and malicious code.

Security of computer systems and files:

- Locking computer systems with a password.
- Ensuring computer software is up to date.
- Protecting servers by power surge protection systems through line-interactive uninterruptible power supply (UPS) systems.
- Implementing password protection and controlled access to data files, for example 'no access', 'read only', 'read and write' or 'administrator-only' permission.
- Controlling access to files, folders, or entire hard drives encryption.
- Not sending personal or confidential data via email or other file transfer means without first encrypting them.
- Destroying data in a consistent manner when needed: deleting files and reformatting a hard drive will not prevent the possible recovery of data; consult our guidance on data disposal.
- Imposing non-disclosure agreements for managers or users of confidential data.

Cloud storage: SHARE POINT (OFFICE 356)

6.1. Compliance with GDPR

6.1.1. Purpose

The project underscores the minimisation and limitation of personal data processing. Though personal data processing is minimal during the research phase, it may be necessary to process data for disseminating project results, such as events, trainings, and publicity activities. Any personal data processed will be strictly necessary for the intended purpose and handled in accordance with GDPR principles.

6.1.2. Accuracy

Acknowledging the significance of data accuracy in GDPR compliance, measures will be implemented to ensure that any personal data collected or processed is accurate, relevant,

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and up to date throughout the project lifecycle. Routine reviews and updates are conducted to maintain data accuracy.

6.1.3. Integrity and Confidentiality

Upholding the integrity and confidentiality of personal data is paramount. All personal data collected or processed will be treated with the utmost confidentiality, and security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access, disclosure, or alteration. Encryption, access controls, and secure storage mechanisms will be employed to safeguard personal data.

6.1.4. Accountability

Maintaining accountability in data processing activities is paramount. Clear roles and responsibilities had been assigned to project team members to ensure compliance with GDPR obligations. Regular audits and assessments will be conducted to monitor compliance and address any issues that may arise.

6.1.5. Personal Information

Any personal information collected will be processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently in accordance with GDPR requirements. Individuals will be informed of the purpose and legal basis for processing their personal data, and their rights regarding their data will be respected at all times.

6.1.6. Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation

Where feasible, personal data will be anonymised or pseudonymised to minimise risks to data subjects. Anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques will be employed to irreversibly dissociate personal data from individual identities, thereby reducing the likelihood of re-identification.

6.1.7. Informed consent

Where necessary, informed consent will be obtained from data subjects prior to the processing of their personal data. Clear and comprehensible information will be provided to individuals regarding the purposes of data processing, their rights, and how their data will be used. Consent will be freely given, specific, informed, and revocable at any time.

7. Ethics

7.1. Data protection

CCRI Knowledge Hub follows a participatory methodology during its whole lifecycle by involving actors from the Quintuple Helix from across Europe. Twenty-five seminars (16 online, 9 face-to-face) and the mentoring programme will be held. Four ethical issues have been identified within the project, namely data privacy, incidental findings, informed consent of participants and ensuring ethical compliance for the solution design:

- Data privacy issues will arise in the context of gathering data of activity in several devices.
- Incidental findings may occur when gathering data from workshops and seminars, even informal encounters, including those concerning to sensitive information (political beliefs may arise in the context of CE debates and potential solutions and policy recommendations)
- Informed consent will be provided for the participation of individuals directly and indirectly involved in all actions and activities planned
- The Ethical Solution Design must address the most important risks linked to the aforementioned activities.

A key aspect of any research involving human beings - beyond the researcher(s) actually conducting the research - is to protect the interests of participants. In regards personal data and data privacy data will be gathered in order to contact with participants recruited; in addition, persons outside the project but participating in the CCRI Knowledge Hub activities are contacted by partners; sometimes, further information or clarifications may be needed, thus personal data (contact information) is collected. These data is used restrictedly for research purposes. Contributions of participants and data gathered during the activities is collected and pseudo anonymised, ready to be shared under Open Access terms, accomplishing the RRI and FAIR principles. Informed consent will be obtained from all participants prior to their participation, whenever necessary: all participants are adults able to give consent.

The ethical solution design is also within the dedicated Ethics and Data Management Plan (T1.5-D1.3) **POTENTIAL IMPACT:** CCRI Knowledge Hub will unveil factors affecting the perception of CE different contexts and socio-historical environments, even different types of stakeholders; whilst the consortium considers the risk of misuse is minimal, certain power imbalance might be reproduced by these findings. The mitigation of this ethical risk relies on the participatory nature and the inclusion of players from the Quintuple Helix fostering genuinely participatory research.

The CCRI Knowledge Hub project is committed to ensuring the highest standards of data protection and privacy for all stakeholders involved. This policy outlines the principles and practices we adhere to protect personal data during the implementation of the project.

Data Collection and Use:

- The CCRI Knowledge Hub project will collect personal data only when it is necessary for the project's objectives, such as stakeholder engagement and collaboration.
- The types of personal data collected may include names, contact information, organisational details, and other relevant information provided voluntarily by the stakeholders.

Lawful Basis for Processing:

- All personal data collected and processed within the scope of the CCRI Knowledge Hub project are handled in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other applicable data protection laws.
- Personal data is processed based on the lawful grounds of consent, contractual necessity, legal obligations, or legitimate interests, as appropriate.

Data Minimisation and Accuracy:

- The CCRI Knowledge Hub project ensures that only the minimum amount of personal data necessary for the intended purposes is collected and processed.
- We are committed to maintaining accurate and up-to-date personal data. Stakeholders have the right to request corrections or updates to their data at any time.

Data Security:

- Appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented to protect personal data from unauthorised access, disclosure, alteration, or destruction.
- Access to personal data is restricted to authorised personnel who require it for the performance of their duties.

Data Retention:

- Personal data will be retained only for as long as necessary to fulfil the purposes for which it was collected or as required by law.
- Once personal data is no longer needed, it will be securely deleted or anonymised.

Rights of Data Subjects:

- Stakeholders have the right to access their personal data, request rectification or erasure, object to processing, and request data portability.
- Requests to exercise these rights can be submitted to the designated Data Protection Officer (DPO) if designated, data controller or data processor of the CCRI Knowledge Hub project.

Third-Party Sharing:

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- Personal data will not be shared with third parties without the explicit consent of the data subjects, except where required by law or necessary for the performance of the project.
- Any third-party service providers engaged by the CCRI Knowledge Hub project will be required to comply with data protection obligations equivalent to those outlined in this policy.

Transparency and Communication:

- The CCRI Knowledge Hub project will maintain transparency regarding its data protection practices and inform stakeholders about how their personal data is used and protected.
- Regular updates and communications will be provided to ensure stakeholders are aware of their rights and any changes to the data protection policy.

By adhering to these principles, the CCRI Knowledge Hub project aims to foster trust and confidence among stakeholders while promoting the CE concept in European cities and regions.

7.1.1. Informed consent

- Procedures for obtaining informed consent:
 - All participants will receive a comprehensive consent form prior to any data collection activities (including research purpose and specific data collected, how data will be stored, processed and used, potential risks associated with participation -if any-, voluntary nature of participation, the right to withdraw consent at any time).
- Consent will be documented through signed forms (signed physical or verified digital confirmation).
- All consent materials will be preserved in secure storage for the duration of the project.
- Withdrawal procedures:
 - Participants will be informed of their right to withdraw consent at any time without penalty.
 - Clear procedures will be established for participants.
 - Upon withdrawal, all identifiable data will be removed from active datasets unless legally required otherwise.
 - Documentation of withdrawal and data removal actions will be maintained.

7.1.2. Confidentiality and Anonymisation

- Confidentiality and protection measures:
 - All data containing personal identifiers will be stored in secured environments with access restrictions
- Anonymisation procedures:

- Personal identifiers will be removed from datasets through systematic anonymisation processes.
- Anonymisation will employ techniques including replacement of direct identifiers with codes or pseudonyms.

7.1.3. Data security

- Technical security measures: multi-factor authentication will be required for accessing sensitive data, regular security updates and patches will be applied to all systems handling project data.
- Administrative security controls: use a strong, unique passwords, follow a “clean desk” policy at the end of each workday, report any suspicious emails or phone calls immediately.

7.1.4. Regulatory Compliance

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union is the primary regulation governing the collection, storage, and use of personal data within the EU. Regarding the project, the GDPR establishes that the processing of personal data must be based on a valid legal basis, such as explicit consent, the execution of a contract, compliance with a legal obligation, the protection of vital interests, the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, and the legitimate interests of the controller.

Additionally, the GDPR promotes essential data protection principles: lawfulness, fairness, and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimisation; accuracy; storage limitation; and integrity and confidentiality. The rights of data subjects, including the right of access, rectification, erasure (right to be forgotten), restriction of processing, data portability, and objection, must be respected.

To ensure compliance with the GDPR at all stages of the project, the following strategies will be implemented in relation to the personal data that may be obtained during the execution of the project:

1. Obtaining Informed Consent (when necessary):

All participants in the project must provide explicit informed consent before the collection of their personal data. Clear and detailed information will be provided on how their data will be used, with whom it will be shared, and their rights under the GDPR. The consent process will be meticulously documented to ensure transparency and accountability.

2. Data Security:

Robust technical and organizational measures will be implemented to protect personal data against unauthorized access, loss, alteration, or destruction. This will include the use of encryption, strict access controls, and updated information security policies. Additionally, periodic security audits will be conducted to identify and address potential vulnerabilities.

3. Data Breach Notification:

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In the event of a personal data breach, the relevant supervisory authority will be notified within 72 hours of becoming aware of the breach. A clear internal procedure will be established to manage and document any security incidents.

4. Coordination and Collaboration among Partners:

Clear data processing agreements will be established among project partners, defining each party's responsibilities regarding personal data management. These agreements will ensure that all partners comply with the GDPR and adopt appropriate measures to protect the data. Furthermore, any transfer of personal data between EU member countries will be conducted in accordance with the GDPR provisions, ensuring an adequate level of protection.

By implementing these strategies, the project will not only comply with the GDPR and other relevant European regulations but also establish a high standard of ethics and responsibility in the management of personal data, protecting the rights and privacy of participants and ensuring the integrity of the project.

7.1.5. Data integrity

- Quality control procedures: data validation rules will be implemented at the point of collection, data cleaning protocols will be established to address anomalies and errors.
- Validation methods: statistical validation techniques will be applied to identify outliers and inconsistencies.

7.1.6. Participant Rights

- Rights management framework: clear procedures will be established for participants to exercise their rights under GDPR, including:
 - Right of access to personal data. Participants can submit access requests via a dedicated email address to CCRIknowledgehub@kveloce.com
 - Right to rectification of inaccurate data: participants can submit corrections forms highlighting specific information requiring updates.
 - Right to erasure: certification of deletion provided to requestor upon competition.
 - Right to restriction of processing.
 - Right to data portability (exporting function allowing data download in common formats).
 - Right to object to processing.

7.1.7. Disclosure and Transparency

- Disclose any potential or actual conflicts of interest related to the research, such as funding from external sources or relationships with stakeholders.
- Plan how you will share research results openly and transparently, whether through publication in peer-reviewed academic journals, presentation at conferences, or publication of data and supplementary materials in public repositories.

7.1.8. Ethical Review

- Review process:
 - Project activities will be reviewed by the PC before data collection begins
 - Data collection templates will include consent sections and privacy notes
 - Any changes to data collection methods will require additional review
- Basic ethical oversight:
 - PC will serve as the main point of contact for ethical concerns.

7.2. CCRI Knowledge Hub Ethics Self-assessment

This section presents the ethics self-assessment of the project that will guide its Ethical Management Plan, a general definition of an ethics management plan, as well as the general and specific objectives and a particular description of the CCRI Knowledge Hub project's ethics management plan.

7.2.1. Objectives

CCRI Knowledge Hub aims to increase the impact of the existing CCRI by enlarging the network of involved stakeholders, bringing together the knowledge and critical mass already developed around CE implementation and building upon the CE stakeholder platform. The ultimate goal is to promote and make the CE concept a reality in European cities and regions.

7.2.2. Methodology

The Ethical Solution Design must address the most important risks linked to the aforementioned activities. A key aspect of any research involving human beings - beyond the researcher(s) actually conducting the research - is to protect the interests of participants.

In regards PERSONAL DATA and DATA PRIVACY data will be gathered in order to contact with participants recruited; in addition, persons outside the project but participating in the CCRI Knowledge Hub activities are contacted by partners; sometimes, further information or clarifications may be needed, thus personal data (contact information) is collected. **These data will be used strictly for research purposes.** Contributions of participants and data gathered during the activities will be collected and **pseudo anonymising, ready to be shared under Open Access terms**, accomplishing the RRI and FAIR principles. INFORMED CONSENT will be presented to all participants prior their participation: all participants will be adults able to give consent.

7.2.3. Potential impact

CCRI Knowledge Hub will unveil factors affecting the perception of CE different contexts and socio-historical environments, even different types of stakeholders; whilst the consortium considers the risk of misuse is minimal, certain power imbalance might be reproduced by

these findings. The mitigation of this ethical risk relies on the participatory nature and the inclusion of players from the Quintuple Helix fostering genuinely participatory research.

7.2.4. Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislation

Ethics is an integral part of research that will be considered from the beginning to the end of the project implementation. CCRI Knowledge Hub fulfils the national legal and ethics requirements of the countries and institutions involved. In this regard, it should be emphasised that all academic and/or research entities involved currently have Ethics Committees. These committees could follow different protocols and approval procedures, but, at first instance, the research entity must justify all issues considering the informed consent and data privacy and pseudo-anonymisation of the information collected exposing why the research to be carried out is necessary, relevant and appropriate. Companies and non-profit entities involved, and also those without an internal Ethical Committee, should guide their procedures in line with the statements and agreements reached during the Ethics Management process, as well as the Ethics framework (T1.5 - D1.3). All the activities developed along the project will comply with ethical principles and relevant national, EU and international legislation, for example, the Chapter of Fundamental Rights of the EU and the European Convention on Human Rights. Provisions of Directive 95/46/EC and the General Data Protection Regulation are shown to be highly relevant to the protection of research participants. THE GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION (GDPR): Observing existing European regulation already provides many safeguards ensuring that data privacy is maintained throughout any research or service delivery process.

The notion of data subjects' consent to processing is to be harmonised and the criterion added consent be "explicit". **The data will be accessible only for the participants involved in the project (this includes the CCRI-CSO)** and no transfer to any third party will be made. During the project, the Project Management Board has to make a decision on the date of destruction. A common trend in this area is to destroy them after 10 years from the project end date. Data controllers will be required to implement conformant policies and processes (Art. 22) including notifying any breach without delay. Data subjects' rights to have data deleted - "right to be forgotten" (Art. 17) - and to receive free copies of their data, are to be strengthened. Privacy impact assessments will be required if processing is deemed risky, and all but the smallest companies must appoint a data protection officer and notify details to their national authority. These provisions will effectively implement an intended 'privacy by design' (Art. 23), though many details remain to be finalised. The draft Regulation gives the Commission powers to extend the rules subsequently by means of delegated and implementing acts. The project coordinator (KVC) commits to following the relevant national legislation supported by all partners - and later EU regulation - where it applies to the work carried out. All measures necessary to implement the appropriate legislation will be taken. DATA PRIVACY As previously introduced, the basic principles for processing personal data centre on transparency, general prohibition, legitimate purpose and proportionality: Transparency: The data subject has the right to be informed when his/her personal data are being processed. General prohibition: Personal data may not be processed unless: a) EXPLICIT CONSENT; b) PROPORTIONALITY

(Personal data may be processed only insofar as it is adequate, relevant and not excessive about the purposes for which they are collected and further processed); c) LEGITIMATE INTEREST (Personal data can only be processed for specified explicit and legitimate purposes and may not be processed further in a way incompatible with those purposes). Incidental findings on sensitive data concerning religious beliefs, political opinions, health, sexual orientation or race are neither required nor scoped within the project thus a general prohibition to collect this information is stated. As is the nature of the minimum harmonisation of the Directive, national regulation may add to the principles set out there, and their jurisdictions may develop particular interpretations of the stipulations in the Directive, after translation and transposition.

7.3. Ethical Management Plan: definition and main aspects

An Ethical Management Plan within a coordination and support project is a structured document that outlines the ethical considerations, principles, guidelines, and procedures that govern the conduct of research activities. It serves as a roadmap for ensuring that the research is conducted in an ethical manner and adheres to established ethical standards, regulations, and guidelines. Overall, an Ethical Management Plan serves to promote ethical conduct, integrity, and accountability in research, ultimately safeguarding the rights and well-being of research participants and upholding the credibility and trustworthiness of the research outcomes.

The Ethical Management Plan is envisaged in deliverable D1.3. together with the Data Management Plan. D1.3 is the main outcome of task 1.5 included in WP1 Project Management and Network coordination – 1. The overarching objectives can be broken down into the following specific objectives:

- Ensure that all aspects of the project, from research to implementation, adhere to ethical principles and standards, including respect for autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, and transparency.
- Engage with a diverse range of stakeholders, including community members, policymakers, and researchers, to solicit input, feedback, and collaboration throughout the project lifecycle with the highest respect by their dignity, privacy and self-determination, also taking into consideration gender aspects.
- Provide stakeholders with accurate and comprehensive information about the project's goals, methodologies, risks, and potential benefits to enable informed decision-making and participation.
- Safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of individuals' data collected during the project. Implement robust data protection measures and ensure compliance with relevant privacy regulations and guidelines.
- Promote equity, diversity, and inclusivity in all project activities.
- Identify and mitigate potential risks associated with the project, including risks to participants' well-being, data security...

- Maintain transparency in decision-making processes, project outcomes, and allocation of resources. Hold the project team and stakeholders accountable for upholding ethical standards and addressing any ethical concerns or violations.
- Regularly assess the project's adherence to ethical principles and standards through monitoring, evaluation, and feedback mechanisms. Use findings to make necessary adjustments and improvements to project activities and processes.

7.3.1. Connexion to CCRI Knowledge Hub WPs

As mentioned, the Ethical Management Plan is designed to cover all activities throughout the project, meaning all foreseen activities within the WPs in which ethical and legal aspects need to be considered and met. Specifically:

WP1-WP5: the primary objectives revolve around monitoring implementation, handling administrative and financial matters, facilitating information exchange, and coordinating with various partners effectively. Ethical concerns arise in ensuring transparency and fairness in monitoring processes, maintaining financial integrity and accountability, safeguarding the confidentiality of shared information, and fostering equitable partnerships with all involved organizations.

WP2: the focus is on compiling practices, expanding the knowledge base, identifying relevant materials, and developing the CCRI Knowledge Hub platform. Ethical considerations include acknowledging intellectual property rights, promoting unbiased knowledge dissemination, ensuring fairness in material selection, and upholding data privacy and accessibility in platform development.

WP3-WP6 aims to evaluate readiness, generate resources, conduct preparatory activities, engage experts, and deliver customised services. Ethical concerns encompass fair evaluation criteria and recommendations, providing stakeholders with accurate and impartial resources, ensuring transparency and fairness in all activities, and selecting experts based on expertise and impartiality.

WP4-WP7 focuses on dissemination, communication, and community management. Ethical considerations include transparency and accuracy in communication efforts, fostering inclusive community management practices, and ensuring that engagement activities are conducted ethically and with integrity.

WP8 objectives are centred around preparing an exploitation and sustainability strategy and extracting recommendations for successful and citizen-supported CE projects and interventions. Ethical considerations in this WP include developing the exploitation strategy transparently and ensuring that it aligns with ethical principles such as fairness, inclusivity, and environmental stewardship. Additionally, extracting recommendations for CE projects should involve engaging stakeholders ethically, respecting their perspectives and contributions, and prioritizing interventions that benefit communities while minimising potential negative impacts.

7.4. CCRI Knowledge Hub ethical monitoring plan

This section presents all actions and tools specifically developed to ensure the application of the following ethical values and the monitoring of ethical issues within the CCRI Knowledge Hub project. Specifically, it outlines the ethics requirements prior to starting project activities involving participants, as well as the tools for monitoring ethics.

Ethical principles/ values that will guide CCRI Knowledge Hub project and its activities:

- **Reliability.** Guaranteeing research quality evident in the design, methodology, analysis, and resource utilization.
- **Honesty.** During the development, execution, review, reporting, and dissemination of research, it is essential to conduct these activities transparently, equitably, comprehensively, and impartially.
- **Responsibility.** Taking responsibility for the project implementation process from inception to publication, including its management and organisation, as well as for training, supervision, and mentorship, and recognizing its broader societal impacts.
- **Quality.** The results of the project must be of high quality and reliability. Consortium partners must ensure that the information collected and derived from the different activities is accurate, current and relevant to the project objectives.
- **Clarity.** The project results should offer accurate and easily comprehensible information, particularly tailored to the intended audience.
- **Respect.** Showing respect for peers, participants, subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment.
- **Informed consent.** Participants involved in the project activities need to comprehensively grasp the consequences of their involvement in the research. The informed consent should explicitly outline participants' entitlement to be informed about the personal data that might be collected. Moreover, it should be evident that they retain the right to decide, consent to, and manage the timing and manner of their active participation in a project.
- **Privacy.** All personal data provided by participants and other stakeholders in the CCRI Knowledge Hub project will be confidentially treated and kept.
- **Gender equality.** In the CCRI Knowledge Hub project, gender balance will be a condition for all activities carried out and especially in those where it can be directly manipulated (e.g. in the recruitment of experts for the mentoring programme).

7.4.1. Ethical requirements prior to activities with participants involvement

As mentioned in the current document, the CCRI Knowledge Hub project will not carry out any activities involving the handling of sensitive personal data such as health data. However, the mere participation of people with different profiles implies the usage of tools that guarantee compliance with ethical and legal standards, thus safeguarding the rights and data of these people. For this reason, prior to starting any activity involving people, the following ethics requirements should be met:

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1. The project coordinator (KVC) should meet with the partner leader of the activity to discuss and check the legal and ethics documents needed prior to start the activity (mainly informed consent and other additional questionnaires that can be required).
2. The partner/s leader of the activity should prepare the needed documents and provide them to the partners involved in the development of the task for them to check, translate and adapt to their context if necessary.

Each partner involved in the development of the task is responsible of using the provided documents and adaptations made to them. The handling and storage of these documents is specified in the sections above.

7.4.2. Ethics monitoring tools

In order to ensure that the CCRI Knowledge Hub project and its results meet the highest ethical standards, two tools have been developed: 1) questionnaire regarding ethical aspects and data protection (Annex 1), and 2) questionnaire to monitor compliance with CCRI Knowledge Hub ethical standards (Annex 2). For greater ease of use and management of these two tools, they will be carried out in an online format.

As for the questionnaire to monitor compliance with CCRI Knowledge Hub 's ethical standards, the main objective is to ensure that CCRI Knowledge Hub 's ethical values have been applied and complied with. Information derived from this questionnaire will be analysed providing an overview of the potential ethical issues arising for the project. The results could be analysed quantitatively and qualitatively. The 5-point scale of response (5 points scale (1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree to 5=strongly agree) will allow to measure ethics risk:

- Scores from 1 to 2 suggest higher ethics risks
- Scores of 3 suggest medium ethics risks
- Scores from 4 to 5 suggest lower ethics risks

Additionally, each question has an associated space for potential comments, giving the opportunity to better detail the ethical risks and propose effective contingency measures, in particular when the score goes to 3 or below. The follow up of the identification, prevention and mitigation of the ethical risks will be reported in the subsequent version of the Ethical Management Plan, including relevant lessons learnt from them.

In Table 4, a summary of the main actions regarding these two tools is presented.

Table 4 Ethics monitoring tools – actions & responsibilities

TOOL	WHO should fill it out (responsible)	WHEN should be fill it out	WHO gather and analyse the information
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Questionnaire about ethical aspects and data protection	Each partner involved in the development of the task/activity involving people	Prior to start an activity	Partner leader of the task/activity gather and analyse the information in order to check if any additional document or action is needed.
Questionnaire to monitor compliance with CCRI Knowledge Hub ethical standards	Each partner organization will fill out questionnaire	Every quarter taking into account the activities/ tasks carried out in that internal reporting period.	Information will be gathered and analysed by CCRI Knowledge Hub Project coordinator.

8. Conclusions

In conclusion, this document establishes a robust framework for data management and ethical compliance within the CCRI Knowledge Hub project. It prioritises data security, confidentiality, and adherence to GDPR and FAIR principles. As a living document, it will evolve in line with ongoing data collection and emerging insights, requiring continuous updates to refine and close all procedures. This iterative approach guarantees that the guidelines remain comprehensive, relevant, and effective, thereby supporting the project's commitment to responsible data handling and ethical integrity.

9. Annexes

9.1. Annex 1: Questionnaire regarding ethical aspects and data protection

QUESTIONS	OPEN ANSWER
The activity to be undertaken should be submitted to a regional or a national ethics committee?	
What are the recruitment criteria (inclusion, exclusion) of the participants?	
How will the participants be recruited?	
Is an informed consent required? If so, who will store and access it, etc?	
Who will collect and store the data?	
What type and formats of data will the project collect?	
Will the data be anonym?	
How will the data be made accessible?	
Which data will be made openly available?	
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	

9.2. Annex 2: Questionnaire to monitor compliance with CCRI Knowledge Hub ethical standards

Ethical values	Question	5 points scale	Comments/indications
Reliability	The design, methodology and analysis of the research carried out so far are based on quality assurance criteria.		
Honesty	The project results clearly state its owner (e.g. European Commission disclaimer)		
	The project results clearly state what is the purpose of the report, toolkit, booklet, or information offered		
	Prior to signing the informed consent form, all participants were provided with details about the project objectives, anticipated outcomes, and scope of the research. They were also allowed the opportunity to pose any questions to the research team.		
	The data, results, methods, and procedures have been accurately reported, ensuring that information from the project has not been fabricated, falsified, or misrepresented.		
	Each participant has received an informational document (or similar) containing all necessary details for participation.		
Quality	CCRI Knowledge Hub results and activities are high in quality and reliability.		
	CCRI Knowledge Hub outputs meet the expected objectives and desired results.		
	CCRI Knowledge Hub results and activities are carried out and/or supervised by a qualified professional(s)		
	CCRI Knowledge Hub results are based on scientific evidence and/or best practices.		

Clarity	Participants involved in the CCRI Knowledge Hub activities have been notified that they can withdraw from the study at any time without facing any repercussions.		
	All project materials (including the informed consent form and other additional documents) have been carefully translated into your local language		
	All project materials (including the informed consent form and other additional documents) have been carefully designed to ensure that the language is clear, easy to read, and appropriate for intended and potential users		
Respect	All project activities undertaken have been carried out respecting participants, subjects, society, cultural heritage and environment,		
Informed consent	All participants engaged in the project activities have signed an informed consent form.		
	All participants engaged in the project activities have received a copy of the informed consent		
	All individuals participating in the project have voluntarily consented to their involvement, demonstrating a thorough comprehension of the research risks and their respective roles within it.		
	The informed consent includes contact data of the relevant research team members for information/questions/complaint/concerns that may arise.		
Privacy	Procedures adopted by the partners for data collection, storage, protection, retention, and disposal adhere to both national and EU regulations.		
	Every precaution has been implemented to safeguard against unauthorized access and utilization of personal data		

	The anonymity and confidentiality of study participants have been ensured throughout all project activities.		
	A description of the personal data processing operations (i.e., actions taken with personal data and their methods) has been facilitated.		
Gender equality	The research teams executing the project comprise an equal balance of genders		
	The research team strives to attain a population with gender balance.		
	Access to project activities has been ensured equally for all participants.		
	Data and information are analysed according to the gender variable		
	Project activities and results use inclusive and non-sexist language and communication		

